

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Integrated weed control in upland rice

J.K. Kehinde and S.O. Fagade, National Cereals Research Institute, P.M.B. 5042, Ibadan, Nigeria

An experiment in 1983 determined the effect of single and combination weed control methods on weed growth, yield, and cost.

Chemical weed control or hand weeding was used singly, combined with each other, and combined with 2 spacings: 30 × 30 cm and 20 × 20 cm. The nine treatments were laid out in a

randomized complete block design with three replications. Cost of land preparation and crop maintenance was assumed to be equal for all treatments.

Propanil was applied at 2.8, 3.0, and 3.6 kg ai/ha.

Major grass species found in experimental fields were *Digitaria horizontalis* and *Eleusine indica*; major broadleaf weeds were *Ageratum conyzoides* and *Boerhavia diffusa*.

A single application of propanil at 3.0 or 2.8 kg ai/ha with 1 hand weeding 40 d after sowing (DAS) was as good as the weed-free control and 2 hand

weedings (see table).

These two treatments controlled weeds better than a single application of propanil at 3.6 kg ai/ha. With the 20 × 20 cm spacing, propanil at 3.0 kg ai/ha controlled weeds better than weeding once 21 DAS.

All treatments involving weeding were relatively expensive because of labor costs. Although one weeding combined with 2.8 kg ai propanil/ha at the 30 × 30 cm spacing gave the highest yield, application of 3.6 kg ai propanil/ha alone gave the highest return. $\mathcal{J}$

Effect of weed control method on upland rice (Faro 11).^a Ibadan, Nigeria.

Treatment ^b	Application		Fresh weed wt (g/m ²)	Yield (t/ha)	Cost of treatment ^c (\$/ha)	Value of yield (\$/ha)	Marginal benefit-cost ratio
	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Time (DAS)					
Propanil, 20 × 20 cm	3.0	14	106.7 b	1.24 a	125	930.00	12.4
Propanil	3.6	14	191.7 c	1.25 a	120	937.50	13.4
Propanil + weeding	3.0	14 & 40	46.7 ab	1.49 a	175	1117.50	8.9
Propanil + weeding	2.8	14 & 40	80.0 b	1.56 a	172	1170.00	9.6
Weeding, 20 × 20 cm	—	21	185.0 c	0.74 b	150	555.00	5.6
2 weedings	—	14 & 40	68.3 a	1.42 a	190	1065.00	7.6
20 × 20 cm	—	—	288.3 d	0.02 c	65	15.00	1
Weedy check	—	—	380.0 e	0 c	50	0.00	0
Weed free	—	14, 35 & 56	17.3 a	1.47 a	235	1102.50	6.0

^aSeparation of means in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. ^bWhere not stated, spacing was 30 × 30 cm. ^cDoes not include cost of land preparation and crop maintenance. Cost of propanil = \$6/liter. Cost of weeding = \$5/man day.

Machinery Development and Testing

Developing an animal-driven pump to draw groundwater

M. A. Baqui, Agricultural Engineering Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

An animal-driven groundwater pump with a positive displacement pumping unit draws and delivers water through reciprocating pistons. The power principle is similar to that used by an animal-driven sugarcane crusher, with a 1:5 speed ratio.

The pump consists of four 15-cm-diameter cylinders fitted with leather-lined bucket pistons. A crankshaft operates the pistons.

The pump was tested by installing it on a 5-cm-diameter, 30-m-deep tubewell. At a bullock speed of 3.8

km/h, the pump discharged 170 liters/min. At a buffalo speed of 5 km/h, it delivered 225 liters/min (Table 1).

The average draft (28 kg) was very low compared to the draft capability of a typical bullock (60 kg).

Table 1. BRRI animal-driven pump performance.^a

Animal employed	Av discharge (liters/min)	Av animal speed (km/h)	Av static water level (m)	Av draft (kg)
Bullock	169.72	3.78	2.95	27.1
Buffalo	224.93	4.98	3.0	27.8

^aMean of 5 observations.